

APPENDIX 2 - SDP2: DETAILED EXECUTION AND ANALYSIS

This Appendix presents a detailed discussion about all the PROV-SwProcess Competency Questions, using data from SDP2 and including the manager's opinion on each of them (the same procedure reported for SDP1 was followed, changing only the scenario and the subject).

Goal 1: Process structure identification during execution and possibilities for process redesign

– **CQ1** *What are the process activities, artifacts, resources, procedures, stakeholders, and the relations among them during the process execution?*

Considering the analysis possibility presented by CQ1 (*It is possible to identify all the process elements that participated in the process execution and the relation among them*) and its respective decision-making possibility (*After identifying the process elements and the relation between them it is possible to find gaps – elements without association or inadequate relation established*), when using iSPuP tool support and the generated macro visualization about SDP2 (shown on Figure 7.13), a grouping of four ellipses can be seen in the lower left corner of this figure. In addition, this group of four ellipses does not have any relation to the other process elements. By hovering over this grouping, the tooltip shown in Figure H.1 is displayed. Based on this, we consider this fact as a gap possibility: three roles informed in the process model were not associated with any of the stakeholders involved in the process (*Test*, *Development_Manager*, and *Support_Manager*) and, in addition, one of the artifacts generated in any of the instances did not have its name informed.

Figure H.1: SDP2 - Tooltip.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- This analysis is correct, because in the provided data, the activities performed by the *Test*, *Development_Manager*, and *Support_Manager* were not informed (as well as artifacts manipulated by them). Regarding the nameless artifact, the manager assumed that this was also in the data, but he could not explain why it happened. Considering that this fact occurs with one artifact, the manager mentioned that this can be treated as an exception. It would be a concern only if such fact was recurring.
- This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- He *can partially* answer CQ1 using his current process management tool - he uses Mantis¹ as BugTracker and a tool developed in his company (called *Head*). Using *Head* he can identify all the elements involved in the process, however, he does not currently have a view (or graph) that relates all of them, as presented by the iSPuP approach.
- Answering CQ1 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ2** Which procedures are used by the process during its execution?

Using SDP2 provided data, CQ2 was not possible to be answered since no procedure was informed in the process execution data. However, as it was done with SDP1, we show to the process manager an analysis possibility in CQ2 using the toy

¹ <https://www.mantisbt.org/>

example, and the following answers were obtained from him (we do not make the question to check if the analysis is correct, considering he does not know in details the process used in the toy - only a quick explanation of it was provided at the beginning of the interview):

- a) -
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *can partially* answer CQ2 through a manual analysis (using queries in SQL), since the company currently controls and stores the procedures used during the process execution (such fact did not occur when the execution data were provided for the analysis in this thesis).
- d) Answering CQ2 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ3:** *Which activities had a high complexity (considering the number of associated stakeholders, artifacts, procedures and / or resources)?*

In order to answer CQ3, the activity’ degree was used. Figures H.2 and H.3 are generated by the visualization tool to support CQ3. The tabular view was used, and we filter all the activities. After that, we order the obtained results by its degree - firstly descending (Fig. 6.17) and, after that, ascending (Fig. 6.18). The first three results obtained are shown in these figures. According to what is shown, it was not possible to perceive any great discrepancy between the levels of activities analyzed (minimum 2 and maximum 3), therefore, it was concluded, through this analysis, that, according to this specific metric (activity grade), none of the activities performed during the 10 instances of the process can be considered more complex than the others.

id	Name	Type	Degree
0	Case_Resolution_7635	Activity	3
3	Case_Resolution_7631	Activity	3
7	New_Feature_Request_7609	Activity	3

Figure H.2: SDP2 – Activities Degree – Part 1.

id	Name	Type	Degree
2	Case_Registration_7602	Activity	2
10	Close_the_Case_7636	Activity	2
16	Close_the_Case_7632	Activity	2

Figure H.3: SDP2 – Activities Degree – Part 2.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- This analysis is *correct*.
- This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- He *can* answer CQ3 using his current process management tool.
- Answering CQ3 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ4:** *Which activities had a high dependency (on other activities)?*

Activities dependency on other activities is provided by PROV-SwProcess Model using the relation *WasInformedBy* (implying that there has been the exchange of some artifact by two activities, one activity using (or changing) some artifact generated by the other activity) and is useful only when just one instance is analyzed. When checking SDP2 instances separately, no dependency between activities was found, because none of the artifacts generated during the 10 analyzed instances was used or modified by another activity in the same instance. We discussed this fact with the manager, and the following points should be considered:

- This fact is *correct*. The manager mentioned that if test activity was considered, for example, this type of dependency would be shown (however, it should be noted that no data were provided regarding the test activity execution).
- It *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- He *can* answer CQ4 using his current process management tool.
- Answering CQ4 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

Goal 2: Understanding stakeholder’s involvement in process execution

– **CQ5:** *What is the activities distribution among stakeholders?*

Figure H.4 is generated by the visualization tool to support in answering CQ5.

id	Name	Type	Degree	Created Artifacts	Modified Artifacts	Associated Activities
22	Person_2	Person_Stakeholder	10	0	0	6
26	Person_5	Person_Stakeholder	13	3	1	4
71	Person_10	Person_Stakeholder	11	2	1	4
69	Team_1	Team_Stakeholder	9	0	0	4
23	Person_3	Person_Stakeholder	7	0	0	4
21	Person_1	Person_Stakeholder	8	0	1	3
13	Person_6	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0	2
15	Person_7	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0	2
16	Person_8	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0	2
25	Person_4	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0	2
42	Organization_3	Organization_Stakeholder	5	0	0	2
17	Person_9	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	1	1
39	Organization_1	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0	1
43	Organization_2	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0	1
45	Organization_5	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0	1
47	Organization_4	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0	1

Figure H.4: SDP2 - Stakeholders X Activities – Tabular View.

Considering the *Person* stakeholders, *Person_2* performed five activities more than *Person_9*, for example. Are these discrepancies really been planned or is it possible to have a better activity distribution among stakeholders during the process instantiation?

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *correct*. The manager said that *Person_2* usually performs more activities because he is assigned only with activities with low level of difficulty, that can be quickly solved. *Person_9*, however, is a system expert and often receives activities that are more difficult and require more time. He mentioned that this analysis would be more complete considering the time spent on each activity.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ5 using his current process management tool.

d) Answering CQ5 is *somewhat relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes. When he gave this response, the manager mentioned that only if the estimated effort and the time spent on each activity was considered, answering CQ5 would be extremely relevant to support in the proposed analysis and decision-making.

– **CQ6:** *Which artifacts are known by a stakeholder, considering that in some process execution he/she created or modified such artifact?*

Figure H.5 is an example of visualization generated by the tool to support answering CQ6. According to this figure, we can see, for example, that only *Person_5* stakeholder manipulated some artifacts like *Honorarios-2.5.08* and *Geral-2.5.08* during the ten analyzed instances, then, we may consider that *Person_5* have some knowledge about them. In the other hand, the artifact *Fiscal-2.5.09* was manipulated both by *Person_5* and *Person_1*, for example. Several other analyzes can be made from the Figure H.5, in relation to artifacts known to stakeholders. In a future instantiation of the analyzed process, if a certain task is associated with a specific artifact (*Fiscal-2.5.09* for example), the process manager can allocate this task to *Person_5* or *Person_1*, considering both of them know this artifact.

Figure H.5: SDP2 – All Stakeholders X Artifacts.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- The presented analysis is *correct*.
- This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.

- c) He *cannot* answer CQ6 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ6 is *very relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ7:** Which stakeholders are out of the average of created and/or modified artifacts?

Figure H.6 is generated by the visualization tool to support in answering CQ7.

Person_5 created 3 artifacts and modified 1 and *Person_10* created 2 artifacts and modified 1. All other stakeholders have only modified one or no artifact. Considering these numbers, we cannot perceive any great discrepancy between the number of artifacts created or modified by the stakeholders and no decision-making is suggested. It is believed (based on the other two case studies scenarios) that if more instances were analyzed, this discrepancy could occur.

id	Name	Type	Degree	Created Artifacts	Modified Artifacts
26	Person_5	Person_Stakeholder	13	3	1
71	Person_10	Person_Stakeholder	11	2	1
69	Team_1	Team_Stakeholder	9	0	0
13	Person_6	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0
15	Person_7	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0
16	Person_8	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0
17	Person_9	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	1
21	Person_1	Person_Stakeholder	8	0	1
22	Person_2	Person_Stakeholder	10	0	0
23	Person_3	Person_Stakeholder	7	0	0
25	Person_4	Person_Stakeholder	4	0	0
39	Organization_1	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0
42	Organization_3	Organization_Stakeholder	5	0	0
43	Organization_2	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0
45	Organization_5	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0
47	Organization_4	Organization_Stakeholder	3	0	0

Figure H.6: SDP2 - Stakeholders X Created and Artifacts – Tabular View.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *correct*.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ7 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ7 is *very relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ8:** *What are the relationships among stakeholders?*

Using SDP2 provided data, CQ8 was not possible to be answered since no relation among stakeholders' roles was informed in the process execution data and this information was not inferred by PROV-SwProcess. However, we showed to the process manager an analysis possibility in CQ8 using the toy example, and the following answers were obtained from him:

- a) -
- b) This analysis *can partially* assist in the proposed decision-making. According to the manager, it is not enough to know the relationship between the stakeholders, it would be necessary to understand the level of this relationship and the reason why it occurs.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ8 using his current process management tool
- d) Answering CQ8 is *somewhat relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes, considering what he said in b).

– **CQ9:** *Which roles does each stakeholder assume?*

Figure H.7 is generated to support in answering CQ9. Using this figure, we can see all the stakeholders that acts as a *Programmer*, as *Support* or as a *Client*. The group of roles in the lower corner of the figure corresponds to the three roles informed in the process model which had no associated stakeholder (based on the provided execution data). According to this figure, we can also see that the most versatile stakeholder is *Person_1*, who acts as *Programmer* and as *Support*, according to the process provenance data. In a next instantiation of this process, if the process manager needs to allocate a *Programmer* or a *Support* person in a specific activity, he knows who can perform these roles, based on previous execution data.

Figure H.7: SDP2 - Stakeholders x Roles.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *correct*; however, it is not common during the process execution that a stakeholder assumes both a *Support* and a *Programmer* role. Besides that, he agreed that this occurred in one of the analyzed instances.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ9 using his current process management tool.

- d) Answering CQ9 is *somewhat relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

Goal 3: Tracking derivations and revisions among artifacts or procedures

- **CQ10:** *Which artifacts are derivations from others?* and
- **CQ11:** *Which artifacts or procedures are revisions from others?*

Figure H.8 is generated by the visualization tool to support the achievement of GOAL 3 (CQ10 and CQ11). Considering this visualization, no derivation between artifacts was found (no association was inferred among the artifacts manipulated by the 10 instances of this process). Although the artifacts used, created and modified by the activities have been informed, it is believed that due to the small number of instances analyzed (10), this fact did not occur.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained (both for CQ10 and CQ11):

- a) This analysis is *correct*, considering only the analyzed group of data.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *can* answer CQ10 and CQ11 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ10 and CQ11 is *very relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

Figure H.8: SDP2 – Artifacts Derivation.